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Comparative microCT analysis of trabecular bone in iliac crest and radius from healthy individuals

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Abstract Text

Introduction: Understanding bone microarchitecture is essential for fracture risk assessment and designing patient-specific bone implants. Although transiliac bone biopsy is used in clinical evaluations, its representativeness for bone microarchitecture at other skeletal sites remains unclear.

Purpose: This study evaluates trabecular bone microarchitecture differences at the iliac crest and the radial head and age-related variations thereof.

Methods: From 12 bone-healthy individuals (two age groups: Group 1: n=6, 60.1±3.9 years, Group 2: n=6, 94.0±0.6 years), bone autopsy samples from iliac crest (n=6/6) and radius (n=4/5) were obtained (ethical approval: EK Nr. 1757/2013). Trabecular bone parameters were computed for the iliac crest biopsy site (cylindric volume with a 7 mm diameter) and for the radial head (cubic volume with 5.7 mm edge length) starting from microCT scans (SCANCO 50, resolution: 24 µm, 90kV).

Results: Trabecular parameters differed significantly between the two anatomical sites. Compared to the biopsy site the radius had lower bone volume fraction (BV/TV, (5.11±1.31)% vs (20.94±7.49)%, p-value<0.0006) and trabecular thickness (Tb.Th, (123±18)µm vs (232±36)µm, p-value<0.0001) as well as higher trabecular separation (Tb.Sp, (956±101)µm vs (765±121)µm, p-value=0.006), while trabecular number (Tb.N) showed no significant differences ((1.01±0.10)mm⁻¹ vs. (0.94±0.09)mm⁻¹, p-value=0.122). Age-related differences showed similar trends at both sites, but were less pronounced at the radius: BV/TV and Tb.Th decreased of -25.21% and -7.09% at the radius as well as of -34.13% and -17.02% at the iliac crest in the older study group. Parameters showed no correlations between sites.

Conclusions: Our findings in healthy individuals suggest that trabecular bone microarchitecture is sparser and age-related bone loss is less pronounced at the radius compared to the iliac crest. The absence of correlations between outcomes of both sites suggests a limited ability of the transiliac biopsy to predict cancellous bone-microarchitecture at the radius, underlining the importance of gaining information of bone structure at fracture-relevant sites.

Iliac crest

Radius

Figure: Iliac crest and radius segmentations of bone samples coming from the same donor with a zoom on the volume of interests used to compute trabecular bone parameters.